

Supplementary Material of the Article « Quantifier les besoins en eau d'une forêt irriguée sous l'effet du changement climatique» (Ehrbar et al. 2026, Swiss Forestry Journal)

Maude Ehrbar^{1,2} and Christine Moos²

1 Office de l'environnement du canton du jura, Bel oiseau 12, 2882 Saint-Ursanne, maude.ehrbar@jura.ch

2 Bern University of Applied Sciences, BFH-HAFL, CH-Zollikofen, corresponding author: christine.moos@bfh.ch

1. Water Balance Model and drought stress index

To calculate the water balance of the current vegetation at the study site in Chillon (VD) under “normal” (i.e., with precipitation) as well as irrigated conditions, we used a simple water balance model following Bugmann & Cramer (1998). This is a refinement of the Thornthwaite water balance model (Thornthwaite & Mather 1955). Although various more complex methods exist to compute the water balance (e.g., Granier et al 1999, Speich et al 2020), Thornthwaite-type methods only require time series of monthly temperature and precipitation (Lutz et al 2010), and, thus, are usable when limited past data is available and to make predictions based on limited future climate scenario output data.

In the used water-balance model, water can be intercepted by vegetation, evaporated from bare soil, stored in the soil as soil moisture, taken up and transpired by vegetation, or a surplus that runs off of the surface (Fig. S1). The calculation requires two time series, mean monthly precipitation and temperature, and two state variables that can vary in space, latitude and soil water-holding capacity.

The monthly potential evapotranspiration (PET_m) is approximated based on a heat index (hi) calculated from the monthly mean temperature (T_m) and corrected for sun angle and day length depending on latitude (lp) and the local topography ($PMod$, slope inclination and aspect) (following Bugmann & Cramer 1998; adapted from Thornthwaite & Mather 1957 and Pastor & Post 1985) as written in Equation 1 (parameters are described in Tab. S1).

$$PET_m = PMod * lp * \left(\frac{10}{hi} \times \max(T_m, 0)\right)^a \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Monthly mean precipitation (P_m) is partitioned in infiltration and interception (I_m , Eq. 4). We thereby considered the interception by the crown canopy ($I_{m,veg}$, Eq. 2) as well as of litter and deadwood ($I_{m,lit}$, Eq. 3). The first is determined as a constant fraction of monthly precipitation, estimated from mean values for broadleaf ($f_{broadleaf}$) and conifer ($f_{conifer}$) species (Miralles 2010). $I_{m,lit}$ was estimated as a fraction of the rainfall penetrating the canopy (f_{litter}).

$$I_{m,veg} = (r_{broadleaf} * f_{broadleaf} + (1 - r_{broadleaf}) * f_{conifer}) * P_m \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$I_{m,lit} = f_{litter} * (P_m - I_{m,c}) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$I_m = I_{m,veg} + I_{m,lit} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

By subtracting the interception from PET_m , the monthly evaporative demand (D_m) is calculated as (Eq. 5):

$$D_m = PET_m - I_m \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The evaporative supply rate S_m is calculated as a linear proportion of the soil moisture of the previous month (SM_m) and the soil water storage capacity (SWC) according to Federer (1982) (Eq. 6):

$$S_m = c_w * \frac{SM_m}{SWC} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

Whereas c_w is a supply rate constant (i.e. maximum rate of evaporation).

Evapotranspiration from the soil E_m is assumed to be the minimum of the demand and the supply (Eq. 7):

$$E_m = \min(S_m, D_m) \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

The soil moisture balance is defined as (Eq. 8):

$$SM_{m+1} = \max(\min(SM_m + (P_m - I_m) - E_m, SWC), 0) \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

The yearly drought stress index DI is finally defined as 1 minus the ratio of the summed monthly evapotranspiration and the summed demand (Eq. 9):

$$DI = 1 - \frac{\sum_n E_m}{\sum_n D_m} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

In contrast to Bugmann & Cramer (1998), the evaporative demand was only considered during the growing period (March to October), while soil moisture balance was calculated throughout the year. We further differentiated between interception of coniferous and broadleaved species and included the interception of litter and deadwood based on Floriancic et al (2022). In the irrigated situation (see Fig. S1), we assumed $P=0$ and $I_{veg}=0$.

Fig. S1: Schematic overview of the water-balance model used to calculate the irrigation need below the highway viaduct (grey bar).

Tab. S1: Parameters of the water-balance model and values used in the study of Ehrbar et al.

Parameter	Description	Value used in Ehrbar et al
PMod	Correction factor for slope and aspect	If $slasp > 0$: $PMod = (1 + 0.125 \times slasp) \times 1.6$ If $slasp \leq 0$: $PMod = (1 + 0.063 \times slasp) \times 1.6$ With: $slasp = -2 * \cos(aspect) * \min(1, \frac{slope}{60})$
lp	Correction for sun angle and day length depending on latitude	$a_m + b_m * k_{thornthwaite}$ with: $a = (-1.1226, 0.9859, 1.0454, 0.9708, 0.9605, 0.9185, 0.9669, 0.9892, 0.9900, 1.0600, 1.0815, 1.1444)$ $b = (-7.3094 \times 10^{-3}, -3.8701 \times 10^{-3}, -4.9231 \times 10^{-4}, 3.5179 \times 10^{-3}, 7.1453 \times 10^{-3}, 8.4718 \times 10^{-3}, 7.6410 \times 10^{-3}, 4.9436 \times 10^{-3}, 1.2 \times 10^{-3}, -2.6256 \times 10^{-3}, -6.3692 \times 10^{-3}, -8.6598 \times 10^{-3})$ $k_{thornthwaite} = \max(latitude, 50)$
hi	Heat index: $hi = \sum_n \max(k_1 * T_m, 0)^{k_2}$	$k_1 = 0.2$ $k_2 = 1.514$
a	Empirical exponent: $a = k_3 * hi^3 + k_4 * hi^2 + k_5 * hi + k_6$	$k_3 = -6.75 \times 10^{-7}$ $k_4 = -7.7 \times 10^{-5}$ $k_5 = -0.01792$ $k_6 = 0.49239$
$f_{broadleaf}$	Mean fraction of monthly precipitation intercepted by canopy of broadleaf species	0.19 in summer, 0 in winter (Miralles et al. 2010)
$f_{conifer}$	Mean fraction of monthly precipitation intercepted by canopy of coniferous species	0.22 (Miralles et al. 2010)
f_{litter}	Mean fraction of monthly effective precipitation (not intercepted by canopy) intercepted by litter and deadwood	0.18 (Florjancic et al. 2022)

2. Validation of the used PET formula

To assess the accuracy of the PET formula used in this study (Eq. 1), we compared the obtained values with monthly PET calculated with the Penman-Monteith formula (Monteith 1965) for a climate station in Villeneuve (VD) (www.agrometeo.ch), which is close to the study area. The Penman-Monteith formula is based on physical processes and recognised as the most accurate method to determine PET (Lebourgeois and Piedallu 2005). However, it requires a larger variety of climate data, such as air saturation deficit and wind speed, which is usually not available for future climate scenarios.

Overall, the monthly PET values calculated based on Thornthwaite's method coincide well with the PET values obtained with the Penman-Monteith method (Fig. S2). Differences are visible from January to June, when Thornthwaite's PET is generally lower than Penman-Monteith PET obtained from the Agrometeo station with a lag of approximately one month. This difference between Thornthwaite's formula and Penman's has been studied among others by Lebourgeois and Piedallu (2005), who explained the lag as a result of the delay of about one month between the rise in spring temperatures and the rise in solar radiation. Since Thornthwaite's formula, contrary to Penman's, is based on temperature without taking

radiation into account, this delay appears. Nevertheless, despite this discrepancy, the values remain sufficiently comparable to be considered valid.

Fig. S2: Average monthly PET from 2013-2022 calculated based on Bugmann and Cramer (1998) (violet) in comparison to monthly PET calculated with the Penman-Monteith formula (Agrometeo.ch; yellow)

3. Determining soil water storage capacity (SWC)

As soil plays a decisive role for both hydrological aspects and the rooting of vegetation, getting a good understanding of the soil conditions was crucial for the project. Therefore, pEaudSol (Maître 2022) took soil samples from 10 soil profiles within the study perimeter (Fig. S3). The investigations focused on the useful rooting depth and the soil water holding capacity of the soils. Texture and skeleton content per horizon and rooting depth were determined on site. Additionally, samples of one or more horizons per profile were examined in the laboratory to determine the proportions of clay, silt, sand and gravel, as well as pH.

These parameters were used to calculate the soil water storage capacity (SWC). The SWC was calculated based on the grain size distribution of the fine soil with deduction of the skeleton content.

More specifically, the grain size distribution was used to classify soils into typical soil texture classes using the Jamagne triangle (Jamagne et al 1977). Each texture is assigned a textural coefficient, which gives an estimate of the proportion of soil volume filled by water retained in the soil and available to roots. This coefficient was used to calculate the SWC (mm) according to the following formula, with Z corresponding to the thickness of the horizon in cm and EG to the volumetric ratio of coarse elements (in %):

For each horizon:

$$SWC_{horizon} = \text{textural coefficient} * z * \frac{100 - EG}{100}$$

Total SWC for the soil corresponds to the sum of the SWC of each horizon.

The soil profiles were finally divided into three groups according to their soil water storage capacity. In the study, SWC values of one representative sample per category were selected. Details of the parameters for the three soils are shown in Tab. S2.

Fig. S3: Picture of the three selected soil profiles: n°5 (SWC = 100 mm); n°9 (SWC = 64 mm) and n°10 (SWC = 34 mm). Source: V. Maître

Table S2: Soil parameters of the three samples used in the model. (Source: adapted from Maître 2022)

Sample	Horizon depth (cm)	Swiss textural triangle	Textural triangle Jamagne	Textural coefficient (Jamagne) (mm/cm)	Stoniness (%)	Soil water storage capacity (SWC) (mm)	Slope (°)	Underground	pH
5	24	Argilo-limoneux IT	ALO	1.7	45	22.4			7.9
	18	Argilo-limoneux IT	ALO	1.7	15	26			7.7
	28	Argilo-limoneux IT	ALO/AL	1.75	60	20.2			7.6
	30			1.75	80	10.5			
	Rate according to Jabiol et al. (2009, 66)								20
Total	100					99.1	34	Altenantion of calcareous marl	
9	15	Limoneux (L)	LSA	1.65	5	23.5125			
	10	Limoneux (L)	LSA	1.65	15	14.03			
	10	Limoneux (L)	LSA	1.65	80	3.3			
	35	Limoneux (L)	LSA	1.65	95	2.89			
	Rate according to Jabiol et al. (2009, 66)								20
Total	70					63.7325	27	Ground moraine	7.7
10	20	Limono-argileux (tL)	A	1.7	40	20.4			
	20	Limono-argileux (tL)	A	1.7	60	13.6			
	(30)	-	A	-	100	0			
	Rate according to Jabiol et al. (2009, 66)								x
Total	40					34	35	Lightly impaired limestone	7.6

4. Analysis of drought stress distribution per species

To determine suitable species for future drought conditions at the study site in Chillon, we analyzed the distribution of the long-term drought stress indices (DI) per species in Switzerland with data from the third Swiss National Forest Inventory (NFI; 2004-2006; Brändli 2010). For each of the NFI plots, we calculated the basal area share of 19 selected species (see Tab. S3) and the yearly DI (see section 1) from 1990 to 2010 based on gridded precipitation and temperature data (MeteoSwiss 2023). The soil water storage capacity (SWC) was derived from the Swiss soil suitability map (BLW 1980). We then analyzed the distribution of the mean, maximum and 95-percentile of the yearly DI per species (Fig. S4, S5). A NFI plot was considered if the respective species had at least a share of 10 %.

We further fitted generalized linear models of the basal area share per species as a function of the drought stress index following Walthert and Meier (2017) (Fig. S6). However, since the effect of the drought stress index was not significant for several species, we focused on the descriptive analysis of the distribution of the drought stress index, as follows.

To leverage the descriptive analysis of the DI distribution, we compared the current and predicted drought conditions at the study site in Chillon to the distribution of the drought stress index per species in Switzerland. This allowed for identification of potentially suitable species for future drought conditions. We therefore divided the species into three groups

according to “low”, “medium” and “high” drought tolerance based on the median of the 95-percentile of the yearly drought stress index (Tab. S3). These groups could then be assigned to varying target values of the yearly drought stress index attained under the irrigation regime. It is important to note that this analogy is only approximate, since the drought stress index in the NFI plots is calculated from imprecise soil data, likely overestimating SWC in steep areas with shallow soils. By way of example, the SWC for our entire study zone is 110 mm based on the soil suitability map, which is slightly higher than the highest value determined in this study based on the soil samples (see section 3). We validated the classification of species’ drought tolerance with literature (e.g., Walthert and Meier 2017; Lauber et al 2018), which also led us to add two species, *Pinus sylvestris* and *Sorbus aria*, to species group 3 (high drought tolerance), although the median of the 95-percentile of the drought stress index was < 0.3. Furthermore, certain groups were complemented with additional species, such as *Taxus bachata* in group 2 (medium drought tolerance) or *Acer opalus* in group 3 (high drought tolerance).

Tab. S3: Median of the mean and the 95-percentile of the yearly drought stress index per species over the years 1990-2010 in Swiss NFI plots with a share of $\geq 10\%$ of the respective species. The color indicates the species groups that were determined in the study of Ehrbar et al. Green = low drought tolerance with median of 95-percentile of yearly drought stress (DI) < 0.2; yellow= medium drought tolerance with median of 95-percentile yearly DI between 0.2 and 0.3; orange = high drought tolerance with median of 95-percentile yearly DI > 0.3. Based on literature and expert estimation, *Pinus sylvestris* and *Sorbus aria* were reclassified to species group 3 (high drought tolerance).

Species	Median of mean yearly DI (1990-2010)	Median of 95% yearly DI (1990-2010)
<i>Abies alba</i>	0.008	0.092
<i>Acer campestre</i>	0.029	0.253
<i>Acer platanoides</i>	0.027	0.193
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	0.012	0.129
<i>Betula pendula</i>	0.044	0.245
<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	0.034	0.213
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	0.020	0.151
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	0.020	0.149
<i>Larix decidua</i>	0.025	0.176
<i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i>	0.079	0.311
<i>Picea abies</i>	0.007	0.078
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	0.042	0.231
<i>Quercus petraea</i>	0.054	0.239
<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	0.127	0.360
<i>Quercus robur</i>	0.027	0.177
<i>Sorbus aria</i>	0.024	0.185
<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	0.005	0.054
<i>Tilia cordata</i> / <i>platyphyllos</i>	0.040	0.215
<i>Ulmus glabra</i>	0.010	0.101

Fig. S4: Distribution of the mean yearly drought stress index between 1990 and 2010 of the NFI plots with a share of $\geq 10\%$ of the respective species.

Fig. S5: Distribution of the 95-percentile of the yearly drought stress index between 1990 and 2010 of the NFI plots with a share of $\geq 10\%$ of the respective species.

Fig. S6: Basal area shares of species as a function of the mean yearly drought stress index fitted with generalized linear models based on Swiss NFI data. Models with significant parameters ($p \leq 0.05$) are marked with a *.

5. Irrigation variants

In the study, additional irrigation variants were tested, of which two are presented here in comparison to the situation with precipitation (Fig. S10). Figure S7 shows the simulations of the drought stress indices of each of these variants until 2100. The variant “goal 0.2” targets a drought stress index of 0.2 under current climate conditions (2013-2022). Therefore, water was distributed throughout the year in proportion to the demand (ETP) (Fig. S8). In the second variant (“even distribution”), the same annual amount of water was supplied as in the first variant (540 mm/year), but with a uniform distribution between April and September (90 mm/month) (Fig. S9).

Fig. S7: 2013–2100 annual drought index trends for three variants and three soil water storage capacity (SWC), calculated for the RCP8.5 model. Only local regression curves are shown.

Fig. S8: Visualization of the monthly water balance for the period 2013–2022 for the irrigation variant “Goal 0.2”, for the soil water storage capacity of 100 mm on top and 34 mm on the bottom. Demand = ETP minus interception; Supply = available water supply; SM = usable water reserve available in the soil. The red areas represent the evapotranspiration deficit.

Fig. S9: Visualization of the monthly water balance for the period 2013–2022 for the irrigation variant “Even distribution”, for the soil water storage capacity of 100 mm on top and 34 mm on the bottom. Demand = ETP minus interception; Supply = available water supply; SM = usable water reserve available in the soil. The red areas represent the evapotranspiration deficit.

Fig. S10: Visualization of the monthly water balance for the period 2013–2022 for the natural situation with precipitation, for the soil water storage capacity of 100 mm on top and 34 mm on the bottom. Demand = ETP minus interception; Supply = available water supply; SM = usable water reserve available in the soil. The red areas represent the evapotranspiration deficit.

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